

1 **Two-stage anaerobic digestion of food waste: Enhanced bioenergy production rate by**
2 **steering lactate-type fermentation during hydrolysis-acidogenesis**

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23 **Abstract**

24 This study proposed a lactate-based two-stage anaerobic digestion (AD) process to enhance bioenergy
25 production rate from food waste (FW) and investigated the effect of inoculum addition and culture
26 pH on hydrolysis-acidogenesis and further methanization. A series of batch fermentations were
27 performed with an enriched lactate-producing consortium and without inoculum addition under
28 controlled (5.7) and uncontrolled pH (initial 6.7) conditions. The interplay between the studied factors
29 dictated the fate of lactate, particularly if it is produced and accumulated in the fermentation broth or
30 is consumed by butyrogenic bacteria. Only the self-fermentation of FW with uncontrolled pH resulted
31 in lactate accumulation (0.2 g/g volatile solid (VS) fed) with limited off-gas production (0.32 NL/L)
32 and VS losses ($\approx 16\%$). Such lactate-rich broth was successfully digested through biochemical
33 methane potential tests, resulting in a maximum bioenergy production rate of 2891 MJ/ton-VS fed
34 per day, which was two-fold higher compared to that achieved by one-stage AD.

35

36 **Keywords:** Biogas; fermentation pathways; food waste; hydrolysis-acidogenesis; methane
37 production; two-stage anaerobic digestion.

38

39 **1. Introduction**

40 Food waste (FW) represents one of the most severe environmental problems faced by the society in
41 the 21st century. FW accounts for $\sim 45\%$ of municipal solid waste and is considered a cross-cutting
42 issue with multiple negative social, economic and environmental implications. For instance, the
43 European Union generates annually ~ 88 Mt of FW, with an associated cost of 143bn € (FUSIONS,
44 2016). The global estimation for the FW generated in 2019 accounts to 931 Mt, which suggests that
45 around 17% of the total amount of food produced globally may be wasted (Forbes et al., 2021).
46 Nowadays, most of the FW is incinerated or landfilled, which entails prohibitive nutrient and
47 energy losses and increases the total global greenhouse gas emissions by 8–10% (Mbow et al.,

48 2019). In addition, FW is a major contributor to soil and water pollution. The United Nations 2030
49 Sustainable Development Goals have included a target to halve the global per capita FW generation
50 at the retail and consumer levels. Likewise, the European Commission is committed to prevent FW
51 generation along the entire food supply chain and to foster the creation of a circular bioeconomy in
52 order to improve the sustainability and well-being of Europe and beyond. In this context, anaerobic
53 digestion (AD) is nowadays the most cost-efficient and eco-friendly technology for recycling
54 carbon, nutrients and energy from unavoidable FW, representing a cornerstone in the transition
55 toward a circular bioeconomy (IEA, 2018; EBA, 2021).

56 Despite the potential of AD to recycle carbon and energy in the form of biogas, the
57 widespread implementation of AD is nowadays limited by the poor robustness of conventional one-
58 stage AD caused by the high hydrolysis and acidogenesis rate of FW, which typically lacks buffer
59 capacity. Unlike one-stage AD configurations, two-stage AD processes allow buffering the acid
60 stage and ensure optimal ecophysiological requirements for the different microbial communities
61 involved, which may ultimately result in an enhancement of the overall process stability and
62 bioenergy production (Shen et al., 2013; Baldi et al., 2019). However, and despite their potential
63 superior performance, there is a scarce implementation of multi-stage systems on industrial or even
64 pilot scales. Therefore, the development of innovative, sustainable and cost-effective strategies for
65 improving AD performance and stability (maximizing bioenergy production) is crucial to ensure the
66 competitiveness of the AD of FW in the context of a circular bioeconomy.

67 Two-stage AD is a sequential process in which hydrolysis and acidogenesis take place in a
68 first reactor generating a hydrolyzed-acidified effluent that is further fed to a second bioreactor
69 where acetogenesis and methanogenesis occurs. It is therefore reasonable to expect that the
70 performance of the first stage may confer specific features to the acidogenic effluent and will
71 ultimately impact the performance of the second stage. However, two-stage AD might be
72 outperformed in terms of bioenergy production by its single-stage counterpart, particularly when

73 high energy losses (production of hydrogen (H₂) and carbon dioxide (CO₂)) occur in the hydrolytic-
74 acidogenic stage (Pipyn and Verstraete, 1981; Lindner et al., 2016; Feng et al., 2020). Therefore, it
75 is imperative to optimize the first stage for the sake of achieving a superior global process
76 performance in the two-stage AD of FW. In this context, lactate has been found to be the most
77 appropriate substrate for methane formation compared to other acidogenic end-products such as
78 butyrate or propionate (Pipyn and Verstraete, 1981; Wu et al., 2016; García-Depraect et al., 2020;
79 Diaz-Cruces et al., 2020; Detman et al., 2021). From a bioenergetic viewpoint, lactate is the most
80 energetically favorable acidogenic end-product for methanization (Pipyn and Verstraete, 1981). The
81 use of acidified FW rich in lactate has indeed been found to mediate higher biogas production in
82 comparison with unfermented FW (Daly et al., 2020, Guan et al., 2021). However, the knowledge
83 of the design and operational conditions required to optimize the lactate type-fermentation of FW is
84 still limited.

85 Herein, the effect of using an enriched lactate-producing consortium as inoculum and
86 operational pH on the acidogenic fermentation of FW was investigated to elucidate how the
87 prevailing culture pH and biocatalyst would affect the carbon and electron flow as well as the
88 microbial community structure involved in lactate-based metabolic pathways. This study also aimed
89 to assess via biochemical methane (CH₄) potential (BMP) tests to what extent the further
90 acetogenic-methanogenic stage might be impacted when the acidified FW has already experienced
91 different fermentation pathways including the lactate-type fermentation. Raw unfermented FW
92 (mimicking one-stage AD) was also tested in parallel for the sake of comparison. Finally, an energy
93 balance assessment was conducted as an attempt to systematically compare the one- and two-stage
94 AD scenarios for fully exploiting the untapped energy potential of FW. This study provided new
95 insights for driving the acidogenic FW fermentation towards a primary lactate-type fermentation
96 and showed the feasibility and kinetic advantage of lactate-based two-stage AD of FW.

97

98 **2. Materials and methods**

99 *2.1 Food waste*

100 Real FW derived from a local restaurant at Valladolid (Spain) was collected and used as the
101 substrate in this study. It mainly consisted of meat, fish, bread, cooked rice, vegetables such as
102 lettuce, fried potatoes, tomato, onion, and oil. The FW was blended with tap water 20% (w/w) using
103 a kitchen blender and stored at -20 °C. The physicochemical characteristics of the thawed FW
104 mixture were as follows: pH 5.5, 430 g total chemical oxygen demand (COD)/L, 72 g soluble
105 DQO/L, total solids (TS) 29.9% w/w, volatile solids (VS) 28.2% w/w, carbohydrates 38.3 % w/w,
106 proteins 33.2% w/w, lipids 22.2% w/w, and ash 6.1% w/w (on a dry weight basis).

107

108 *2.2 Set up and operational conditions of the hydrolytic-acidogenic stage*

109 A series of batch fermentations were performed in duplicate to evaluate the effect of pH and
110 biocatalyst on the hydrolysis-acidogenesis of FW. The experiments were carried out in a
111 temperature-controlled room (36 ± 1) using two 1.25-L polyvinylchloride gas-tight bioreactors with
112 a working volume of 0.7 L and magnetically stirred at ~300 rpm. Each bioreactor was equipped
113 with a pH controller (EVopH-P5, BSV Electronic, Spain), sampling ports for the liquid and gas
114 phase, and an in-house automatized gas flow meter which is based on the principle of liquid
115 displacement. The fermentation conditions included i) uncontrolled pH with inoculum addition, ii)
116 uncontrolled pH without inoculum addition, iii) controlled pH with inoculum addition and iv)
117 controlled pH without inoculum addition. Operational pH was adjusted at 5.7 ± 0.1 using 6 M
118 NaOH, while the initial pH for the uncontrolled pH condition was 6.7 due to the addition of 5 g/L
119 sodium bicarbonate (buffering agent). Those selected fermentations were inoculated at 20% v/v.
120 The acidogenic inoculum was a heat-shock (90 °C for 20 min) pretreated digestate derived from a
121 pilot-scale anaerobic digester treating FW under mesophilic conditions. The TS content of all
122 fermentations was initially adjusted to 10% using tap water. Gas and liquid samples were taken over

123 72 h to determine gas composition and metabolic end-products. At the end of the fermentation, the
124 culture broth was recovered, characterized for VS content and organic acids profile, and preserved
125 (for two weeks) at 4 °C to avoid any possible change in the organic acids produced prior BMP tests.
126 Analyses performed before initiation of the BMP tests indicated that neither the VS content nor the
127 organic acid profile of the acidogenic broths changed during this low temperature storage.
128 Additionally, the microbial community structure of the acidogenic inoculum, the autochthonous
129 microflora of the (frozen) FW, as well as of the hydrolytic-acidogenic process carried out at the
130 different conditions tested was analyzed. The sampling points for microbial analysis were taken at
131 different times, namely 31.5 (non-controlled pH with inoculum), 32.5 (controlled pH with
132 inoculum) and 40 h (controlled pH without inoculum), which corresponded to the cultivation times
133 near the maximum lactate uptake rate computed (see Supplementary information). Likewise, the
134 reactor sample for microbial analysis in the self-fermentation conducted under uncontrolled pH
135 conditions was drawn at 22.5 h, which corresponded to the cultivation time of maximum lactate
136 accumulation rate.

137

138 *2.3 Set up and operational conditions of the acetogenic-methanogenic stage*

139 BMP tests were carried out as an attempt to evaluate the methanization of the four different
140 acidogenic effluents harvested and of the raw unfermented FW. The tests were carried out in
141 triplicate in 120-mL gas-tight glass serum flasks (50 mL working volume) incubated in an orbital
142 shaker at 120 rpm and 36 ± 1 °C. Digestate from a pilot-scale anaerobic digester treating FW under
143 mesophilic conditions was used as the methanogenic seed. This inoculum exhibited a VS/TS ratio
144 of 0.6 and a slightly alkaline pH of ~ 7.8 . The anaerobic sludge was preincubated for 7 days at $36 \pm$
145 1 °C to reduce the background (endogenous) biogas production and then amended with sodium
146 bicarbonate (5 g/L). The food-to-microorganism (F/M) ratio (on VS basis) was adjusted to 0.25.
147 Flasks were flushed with pure helium gas (Abello Linde, Barcelona, Spain) for 1 min to completely

148 remove all residual oxygen from the headspace. The assays were incubated for 24 days, the
149 incubation time when BMP curves plateaued. Blank tests with only inoculum were carried out in
150 parallel to correct for the endogenous CH₄ production, while positive tests with cellulose pointed
151 out the good quality of the methanogenic inoculum (318 ± 8 NmL CH₄/g VS). The CH₄ recovery
152 rate (biodegradability) was estimated as the ratio between the experimental CH₄ yield and the
153 theoretical CH₄ yield based on the structural characterization of the FW, according to Cheng and
154 Liu (2012). Finally, an energy balance analysis was conducted on the basis of one ton of VS fed, the
155 VS loss recorded during the first hydrolytic-acidogenic stage and the maximum volumetric H₂ and
156 CH₄ production rates. Higher heating values of 12.74 kJ/NL and 35.16 kJ/NL were herein used for
157 H₂ and CH₄, respectively (Diaz-Cruces et al., 2020).

158

159 *2.4 Analytical procedures*

160 Organic acid concentrations (formic, acetic, lactic, propionic, iso-butyric, butyric, iso-valeric,
161 valeric, iso-caproic, hexanoic and heptanoic acid) were measured in an Alliance HPLC system
162 (Waters e2695, USA) equipped with a UV-VIS detector (Alliance 2998 PDA, Waters, USA) set at
163 214 nm and a precolumn Micro-Guard Cation H⁺ Refill Cartridge of 30 × 4.6 mm coupled with an
164 Aminex HPX-87H chromatographic column (Bio Rad, USA). The column temperature was kept at
165 75 °C, while the eluent was 25 mM H₂SO₄ at a flow rate of 0.7 mL/min. A standard mix (Sigma-
166 Aldrich part number CRM46975, USA) and sodium L-lactate (Sigma-Aldrich part number 71718,
167 USA) were used for the calibration curves. Gas composition (H₂, CO₂, CH₄) was analyzed using a
168 Varian CP-3800 gas chromatograph (Varian, USA) equipped with a thermal conductivity detector
169 and a Varian CP-Molsieve 5A Capillary Column (15 m, 0.53 mm, 15 μm) interconnected with a
170 Varian CP-PoreBOND Q Capillary Column (25 m, 0.53 mm, 10 μm), and calibrated using certified
171 standard gas mixtures of known composition (70.0% H₂ and 30.0 CO₂; 70.53% CH₄, 24.0% CO₂,
172 2.99% N₂, 2.0% H₂S, 0.49% O₂). Ultra-pure helium gas was used as the carrier gas at 13 mL/min.

173 Cumulative CH₄ production was estimated by manometric and gas-chromatographic methods, as
174 reported elsewhere (García-Depraect et al., 2022). CH₄ yields were calculated according to Diaz-
175 Cruces et al. (2020). Total carbohydrates were analyzed by the phenol-sulfuric method, while the
176 protein content was estimated from total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN) determination using a conversion
177 factor of 6.25. The lipid content determination protocol of the Regional Service for Agri-food
178 Research and Development (SERIDA, Spain) was used to measure the lipid content of the blended
179 FW. COD, pH, solids and TKN were measured according to standard methods (APHA, 2005). All
180 reagents used herein were of analytical grade.

181 Microbial community structure was determined by amplifying the V3-V4 region of the 16S
182 rRNA gene using the primer set 341F-805R, according to the 16S Metagenomic Sequencing
183 Library Illumina15044223 B protocol (Klindworth et al., 2013). The sequencing data obtained were
184 analysed into the QIIME2 platform (Bolyen et al., 2019). Clean amplicon sequencing variants
185 (ASVs) were annotated against NCBI 16S rRNA database version 2021 at a 97% similarity, while
186 SILVA database v.138 was used for those ASVs assigned with < 97% identity. Data was
187 normalized using rarefaction technique from Phyloseq R package to perform alpha diversity
188 analysis (Weiss et al., 2017). Shannon-Wiener and Simpson (1-D) diversity indices were calculated
189 using Past software (version 4.09).

190

191 **3. Results and discussion**

192 *3.1 Operational performance of the hydrolytic-acidogenic stage*

193 The influence of both inoculum addition and pH control on the hydrolysis-acidogenesis of FW was
194 initially evaluated in terms of the acidogenic off-gas production (Fig. 1a–d, Table 1). In this
195 context, both studied factors had a clear effect on the extent and rate of biogas production and its
196 composition. A higher cumulative production of biogas of up to 5.9 ± 0.5 NL and of H₂ of up to 2.1
197 ± 0.4 NL (equivalent to 31.2 ± 6.4 NmL/g VS added) was computed in the inoculated reactors

198 regardless of the pH condition (Fig. 1). The H₂ content in the acidogenic off-gas peaked at 46–53%
199 and was higher in the inoculum-aided fermentations compared with the self-fermentations, while no
200 CH₄ was detected under the conditions studied (Table 1). Remarkably, the self-fermentation
201 (without inoculum addition) of FW allowed for a lower loss of carbon and reducing equivalents as
202 gaseous CO₂ and H₂, respectively, compared with the inoculum-assisted fermentations regardless of
203 the pH conditions (Table 1). The lowest biogas production (0.27 NL) was observed under non-
204 controlled pH and without inoculum addition, which indeed prevented the onset of H₂ production
205 (Fig. 1b). This carbon and energy saving condition seems a favorable scenario to enhance CH₄
206 production in the second methanogenic stage, as more energy-rich acidogenic effluents with
207 reduced compounds such as lactate were obtained (Chakraborty et al., 2022; García-Depraect et al.,
208 2020).

209 At this point it should be highlighted that the ultimate goal of this study was to enhance the
210 CH₄ production kinetics from FW by steering the lactate-type metabolic pathway during hydrolysis-
211 acidogenesis rather than the production of biogenic H₂. Nevertheless, it was interesting to observe
212 that the bioconversion of FW into H₂ proceeded through the lactate-driven dark fermentation
213 process, even despite the operational pH decreased down to ~4.2 (Figs. 1a and 2a). Similar results
214 have been reported previously by Kim et al. (2012). Nonetheless, the hydrogenogenic activity was
215 evident when the initial pH was near to neutral (~6.7) with the aid of a pH buffer and totally
216 inhibited when FW with no pH adjustment (initial pH 5.3–5.5) was used, as discussed below.

217 The differences in the production of biogas and H₂ herein observed could be explained by
218 considering two aspects. On one hand, the addition of an inoculum harboring vigorous acidogenic
219 microorganisms, including H₂-producing bacteria (as will be discussed in Section 3.1.2), boosted
220 the acidogenic off-gas production, as previously observed by Favaro et al. (2013). The VS reduction
221 efficiency was always higher in the inoculated fermenters (32.7 vs. 15.9% and 50.9 vs. 42.6% for
222 uncontrolled- and controlled-pH conditions, respectively; Table 1), indicating high hydrolytic-

223 acidogenic activity. Such VS destruction values were similar to those previously found during the
224 acidogenesis of FW, which have been reported to range between 26 and 50% (Kim et al., 2009;
225 Moon et al., 2015). On the other hand, it is well established that the pH of the fermentation broth is
226 one of the major influencing factors in the performance of acidogenic systems (Daly et al., 2020;
227 Infantes et al., 2011; Sarkar et al., 2021), and thus it also affected the extent and rate of the evolved
228 biogas (Table 1).

229 The acidogenic reactors operated under controlled pH conditions kept a constant pH value
230 of ≈ 5.7 , with slight deviations of ± 0.1 (Fig. 1a, c), which supported the growth and maintenance of
231 hydrolytic-acidogenic bacteria in addition to H₂ production (García-Depraect et al., 2021). In the
232 uncontrolled pH tests with and without inoculum addition, the initial pH of the fermentation broth
233 experienced a rapid drop during the first 24 h of fermentation, from 6.7 to pH values close to 4.0.
234 Afterwards, the pH tended to increase up to 4.7 in the inoculum-assisted fermentations but,
235 conversely, it went down to 3.5 in the self-fermentations (Fig. 1a, b). The sharp decline in pH was
236 attributed to the accumulation of lactate (pKa 3.8) mediated by the vigorous activity of lactic acid
237 bacteria (LAB) (Yang et al., 2022). The slightly increase in pH was attributed to the consumption of
238 lactate, as observed elsewhere (Blanco et al., 2019), mainly by lactate-consuming H₂-producing
239 bacteria (García-Depraect et al., 2021). Little or no biogas production occurred when no pH
240 buffering agent (sodium bicarbonate) was added even in inoculated fermenters (data not shown),
241 pointing out that both the initial and operational pH impacted the metabolic flux. Therefore, the
242 production of biogas or H₂ herein recorded cannot be explained only by considering the
243 bioaugmentation of specialized microorganisms but its interplay with the operational pH.

244

245 *3.1.1 Metabolic end-products distribution: the key role of lactate during the acidogenesis of FW*

246 The fermentation product spectra recorded during the batchwise acidogenesis of FW are represented
247 in Fig. 2. Both the inoculum addition and pH control influenced the prevailing acidogenic metabolic

248 pathways. Hence, lactate and butyrate were the two major organic acids detected at the end of the
249 batch tests, with concentrations as high as 19.1 (0.2 g/g VS fed) and 13.0 g/L (0.14 g/g VS fed),
250 respectively. However, there was a trade-off between such end-products: the higher the butyrate
251 concentration, the lower the lactate titer and vice versa. The time of incubation and the condition
252 tested (i.e., prevailing biocatalyst and pH) determined whether lactate or butyrate was the major
253 end-product. Acetate, formate and propionate were also detected, and their concentrations
254 fluctuated between 0.4 and 8.9 g/L, 0.2 and 2.1 g/L, and 0.9 and 3.2 g/L, respectively, depending on
255 the condition tested. This indicated the presence, yet to a minor extent, of other side acidogenic
256 metabolic pathways such as mixed-, acetic- and propionic-type fermentation pathways (Zhou et al.,
257 2018). The relatively high acetate concentrations recorded (particularly in fermentations performed
258 under pH-controlled conditions) could be also evidence of homoacetogenesis, explaining the low H₂
259 production recorded. At the end of the test, the self-fermentation with pH control exhibited a
260 slightly higher organic acid yield (350.4 ± 52.7 mg CODeq/g VS fed with an associated
261 acidification rate of $\approx 23\%$) in comparison with the other conditions tested (Table 1).

262 Overall, two different metabolic pathways for lactate were observed, i) the fermentation of
263 carbohydrates into lactate via homolactic, heterolactic, or Bifidus pathway (García-Depraet and
264 León-Becerril, 2018) and ii) the fermentation of lactate into butyrate with the coproduction of H₂
265 and CO₂ (Diez-Gonzalez et al., 1995; Matsumoto and Nishimura, 2007). The oxidation of formate
266 catalyzed by the enzyme formate hydrogen lyase (FHL) might have also contributed to produce H₂,
267 although to a lesser extent than the lactate-driven H₂ production. Interestingly, all the conditions
268 tested diverted the metabolic flux towards the accumulation of lactate during first 20 h of culture,
269 and afterwards towards its metabolization via the butyrate-type fermentation (Fig. 2a,c,d), except
270 for the FW fermentation carried out with no addition of inoculum and without pH control. This
271 latter condition resulted in a prominent build-up of lactate during the first 48 h of culture, which
272 remained essentially constant until the end of the fermentation (Fig. 2b). Interestingly, the test

273 carried out under pH-controlled conditions with the addition of inoculum showed the fastest lactate
274 production and consumption rates, peaking at 1.5 and 1.2 g lactate/L-h, respectively, which
275 corresponded to the highest VS removal, as discussed earlier. A higher FW-to-lactate bioconversion
276 is typically linked to a higher hydrolytic activity (Peinemann et al., 2019), but hydrolysis and
277 consequently LAB growth and lactate production are commonly impaired when uncontrolled pH
278 decreases below pH 4 (Tang et al., 2017). The second highest lactate production rate (0.59 g
279 lactate/L-h) was found when indigenous microorganisms grown under uncontrolled pH conditions,
280 showing good autochthonous microbial activity for the spontaneous lactate fermentation.
281 Comparatively, the other combinations applied entailed, in average, lower lactate
282 production/consumption rates (see Supplementary information).

283 Accordingly, the sequential two-stage lactate fermentation has been reported elsewhere in
284 studies aimed at producing H₂ via dark fermentation (Asunis et al., 2019; Blanco et al., 2019;
285 García-Depraect et al., 2019; García-Depraect and León-Becerril, 2018). From a microbiological
286 point of view, the metabolic patterns observed herein could be explained by reaction time-
287 dependent successions of bacterial communities. It has been shown that LAB produce lactate as the
288 main end-product from the acidogenic breakdown of carbohydrates during a first fermentation step,
289 and the produced lactate is then metabolized by butyrogenic bacteria such as *Clostridium butyricum*
290 and related species during a secondary lactate fermentation (García-Depraect et al., 2019). The
291 balance between such microbial groups (i.e., LAB and butyrogenic bacteria) is typically pH-
292 dependent (García-Depraect et al., 2021). Compared to spontaneous lactic acid fermentation,
293 bioaugmentation of LAB has been proven as a useful strategy to achieve enhanced lactate
294 production yields (Zhang et al., 2021). However, the presence of the autochthonous communities in
295 non-sterile fermentations may influence the fermentation outcome even when adding an external
296 workhorse (Peinemann et al., 2019). Accordingly, it could be inferred that both the acidogenic
297 microbial consortium used in this study and the indigenous microflora present in the FW harbored

298 the metabolic potential to perform the sequential two-stage lactate fermentation. In this context, the
299 accumulation of lactate ($76.3 \pm 1.9\%$ selectivity) was favored when the secondary lactate
300 fermentation was prevented, a fact that seems challenging but was achieved herein by
301 spontaneously fermenting FW under non-controlled pH conditions. Tailored environmental and
302 operational conditions, such as a low pH and/or short reaction time, have been also proven to
303 increase lactate selectivity (Feng et al., 2018; García-Depraect et al., 2020).

304

305 3.1.2 Acidogenic microbial community analysis

306 Bridging microbial insights with process engineering helps to attain a better understanding
307 of the hydrolysis-acidogenesis of FW. The microbial diversity of the inoculum included genera
308 belonging to *Lactobacillus*, *Klebsiella*, *Clostridium*, *Stenotrophomonas*, *Acinetobacter*, with
309 relative abundances of 55.2, 28.0, 10.9, 3.0 and 1.8%, respectively, together accounting for > 99%
310 of the total community (Fig. 3). Other satellite bacteria with a relative low abundance (< 1.0%)
311 were *Brucella*, *Curvibacter*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Methylobacterium*. Notably, *Pseudomonas* was the
312 only microorganism amongst such subdominant bacteria that was detected at high relative
313 abundances (> 1%) in the hydrolytic-acidogenic process, particularly when pH was not controlled.

314 *Pseudomonas* was part of the autochthonous microbiota present in the FW employed (16%
315 relative abundance). In the FW, *Lactobacillus* was the most dominant bacterial genus, accounting
316 for 41.1% of the total reads, which was a reasonable result since FW is a good growth medium for
317 this LAB, which indeed is well-known for being among the most dominant spoilage
318 microorganisms in the spontaneous fermentation of carbohydrates-rich substrates such as FW (Im et
319 al., 2020; Wu et al., 2018). The microbiota of the substrate also harbored bacterial genera belonging
320 to *Leuconostoc* (15.0%), *Serratia* (7.0%), *Rahnella* (5.4%), *Brochothrix* (5.1%), *Erwinia* (4.4%)
321 and *Weissella* (3.5%). Interestingly, all such bacteria were detected during the hydrolytic-
322 acidogenic stage, particularly in tests conducted without pH control, with relative abundances lower

323 than 10% except in the case of *Leuconostoc* (10.8–12.7%). That prevalence of autochthonous
324 microbiota evidenced that the prevailing bacteria during the hydrolytic-acidogenic stage might
325 originate, at least partially, from the FW itself, thereby leading to an open fermentation system.

326 It was also found that regardless of the inoculation of the hydrolytic-acidogenic fermenter,
327 pH-uncontrolled conditions led to a relatively higher diversity and evenness of the communities
328 compared to those prevailing under controlled pH, as evidenced by the Shannon and Simpson
329 diversity indices (see Supplementary materials). Therefore, the controlled and uncontrolled pH
330 regime determined in some extent clustering in the microbial communities, as supported by the
331 hierarchical clustering analysis (see Supplementary materials). Under non-controlled pH conditions,
332 the addition of inoculum resulted in a microbial community harboring *Lactobacillus* (43.9%),
333 *Klebsiella* (15.7%), *Leuconostoc* (12.7%), *Pseudomonas* (6.6%), *Serratia* (3.4%), *Bacteroides*
334 (3.2%), *Clostridium* (2.5%), *Rahnella* (2.4%), *Brochothrix* (2.2%), *Erwinia* (2.2%), and *Weissella*
335 (1.6%). Comparatively, the microbial community in the fermenter was still dominated by
336 *Lactobacillus* (32.2%) in the absence of inoculum, followed by *Clostridium* (26.9%), *Leuconostoc*
337 (12.7%), *Pseudomonas* (9.9%), *Serratia* (6.0%), *Rahnella* (5.4%), *Weissella* (2.7%), and *Erwinia*
338 (1.7%). The acid-tolerance mechanisms against low pH stress developed by certain acidogenic
339 bacteria may explain in part the relatively higher species diversity found herein under non-adjusted
340 pH conditions, characterized by experiencing a sharp pH drop down to 3.5–4.7 mainly due to lactate
341 accumulation. In fact, some acidogenic bacteria such as *Lactobacillus* can exhibit a relatively high
342 microbial activity at low pH of 4.0 (Wu et al., 2015). Obviously, the prevailing pH widely varied
343 under non-controlled pH conditions in comparison with pH-controlled conditions, and such
344 dynamic pH microenvironment (broader pH range) might enable the growth of different types of
345 microorganisms, which represents another possible explanation for the higher microbial diversity
346 observed.

347 Interestingly, the dominant bacteria at a fixed pH of 5.7 ± 0.1 were *Lactobacillus*,
348 *Bifidobacterium* and, in a minor extent, *Clostridium*, representing 88.1 and 96.6% of the total
349 community in the inoculum-aided fermentation and the self-fermentation, respectively (Fig. 3).
350 Unlike *Lactobacillus*, *Bifidobacterium* is typically more sensitive to low pH stress (Ventura et al.
351 2011), thus it tends to growth better under slightly acidic environments (Wu et al., 2015),
352 explaining why it became dominant at adjusted pH of 5.7 ± 0.1 while its relative abundance
353 remained below 1.0% when pH dropped down to 3.5–4.7. *Klebsiella* was also found to be an
354 accompanying bacterium but only in inoculated fermentations.

355 In general, both the off-gas production and the metabolic spectra observed during the
356 hydrolytic-acidogenic stage were clearly endorsed by the microbial communities identified.
357 Particularly, the production of lactate was evidently explained by the primary dominance of
358 *Lactobacillus*, the lactate producer par excellence. Besides, *Leuconostoc* is a heterofermentative
359 LAB that can produce acetate/ethanol and CO₂ in addition to lactate and is commonly found in FW
360 fermentations (Wu et al., 2018, 2015). Likewise, the *Bifidobacterium* genus is often regarded as a
361 member of LAB with saccharolytic activity that can perform the Bifidus pathway, thus producing 1
362 mol of lactate and 1.5 mol of acetate from 1 mol of glucose (Cheng et al., 2008). Meanwhile,
363 *Klebsiella* and *Clostridium* are well-known H₂ producers, fulfilling the H₂ production function. It
364 has been previously reported that *K. pneumoniae* is equipped with the FHL complex, which is the
365 main responsible of its H₂ production capacity (Jung et al., 2014). On the other hand, some strains
366 of *Clostridium* such as *C. butyricum* and *C. tyrobutyricum* can consume lactate (commonly along
367 with acetate) to produce H₂ with concomitant butyrate and CO₂ production (Matsumoto and
368 Nishimura, 2007), thus interacting with LAB by cross-feeding interactions (García-Depraect et al.,
369 2021). Finally, it is worth noting that satellite bacteria could have a significant role in the
370 acidogenic process despite their lower abundance. For instance, *Pseudomonas* is a facultative
371 anaerobe commonly detected in anaerobic fermenters wherein it can help strict anaerobes to thrive

372 by consuming residual oxygen and by breaking down complex organic substrates (Hung et al.,
373 2011).

374

375 *3.2 Biochemical methane production tests: assessing single- and two-stage AD*

376 The different conditions applied in the hydrolytic-acidogenic stage induced a markedly
377 effect on the subsequent production of CH₄, especially in its kinetics (Fig. 4). Overall, the CH₄
378 yields achieved after 24 days of incubation in the two-stage AD processes ranged from 382.6 to
379 425.3 NmL/g VS added depending on the prevailing conditions experienced during hydrolysis-
380 acidogenesis. The highest CH₄ yield recorded (corresponding to 82.3% CH₄ recovery rate) was
381 attained by inoculating the hydrolytic-acidogenic reactor while keeping the pH constant, whereas
382 self-fermentation resulted in the lowest CH₄ conversion (with an associated CH₄ recovery rate of
383 74.2%) regardless of the pH control strategy implemented (Fig. 4a). Comparatively, raw
384 unfermented FW supported 370.6 ± 1.9 NmL CH₄/g VS added (71.2% CH₄ recovery rate), which
385 was in close agreement with the typical CH₄ yields (200–500 NmL CH₄/g VS) reported in literature
386 for the one-stage AD of FW (Chakraborty et al., 2022). In terms of CH₄ yield, the two-stage AD
387 configuration outperformed its one-stage counterpart by $\approx 13\%$ under optimal conditions. This
388 enhancement in CH₄ production by physically separating hydrolysis-acidogenesis from
389 acetogenesis-methanogenesis lies within the values reported elsewhere for two-stage AD systems.
390 For instance, Baldi et al. (2019) conducted a comparative study of one- and two-stage AD
391 bioreactors continuously treating FW under mesophilic conditions and reported an enhancement of
392 6.0% in CH₄ production by implementing a sequential process. Similarly, De Gioannis et al. (2017)
393 found that a two-stage process recovered 19% more CH₄ from FW than one-stage AD.

394 The different conditions imposed in the hydrolytic-acidogenic stage also supported different
395 CH₄ production kinetics (Fig. 4b), indicating that the first hydrolysis-acidogenic step must be
396 optimized in order to mediate an enhanced bioenergy production rate. As shown in Table 2, the

397 maximum daily specific CH₄ production rate (*R_m*) was estimated by adjusting the CH₄ yield data
398 computed over time to the modified Gompertz model (Diaz-Cruces et al., 2020), which correlated
399 the experimental data more accurately than the first-order kinetic model or the logistic model (data
400 not shown). The methanization of raw FW resulted in a maximum CH₄ production rate of 42
401 NmL/g VS added-day, which was very similar to the 43.3 NmL/g VS added-day mediated by the
402 fermentation broth resulting from inoculated acidogenic tests with pH control. Interestingly, the two
403 highest *R_m* values (109.9 and 97.6 NmL CH₄/g VS added-day) were recorded using the
404 fermentation broths derived from the hydrolytic-acidogenic stage conducted without pH control
405 regardless of the initial inoculation strategy. The higher *R_m* recorded with the lactate-rich
406 acidogenic broth (self-fermentation without pH control) could be explained by the fact that the
407 acidogenic stage dominated by lactate accelerated the hydrolysis of FW while conserving more
408 energy in the substrate (only 15.9% VS loss) to be methanized. From a bioenergetic point of view,
409 acetogenic bacteria and methanogenic archaea can obtain more energy when lactate is the
410 acidogenic end-product. Primary lactate-type fermentation entails a value of Gibbs free energy
411 change (ΔG^0) of -65.8 kJ (at standard physiological conditions) per mol of CH₄ produced, which is
412 more negative than those from butyric-type fermentation (-32.6 kJ), acetic-type fermentation (-31
413 kJ), propionic-type fermentation (-32.1 kJ), and ethanol-type fermentation (-59.4 kJ) (Pipyn and
414 Verstraete, 1981). Furthermore, the anaerobic oxidation of lactate produces acetate, H₂ and CO₂,
415 which are immediate CH₄ precursors that can be simultaneously and rapidly metabolized by
416 aceticlastic and hydrogenotrophic methanogens, respectively. This might ultimately foster
417 syntrophic methanogenesis.

418 At this point it is worth noting that the corresponding final pH during the BMP tests
419 remained at 7.5 ± 0.1 (Table 2). Such pH values are conducive for methanogenesis (De Gioannis et
420 al., 2017), while no organic acids accumulation was detected at the end of all BMP tests (data not
421 shown), implying high syntrophism among microorganisms. Unlike lactate oxidation, lactate

422 accumulation may onset the formation of propionate at high partial H₂ pressures (> 0.1 kPa) (Wu et
423 al., 2016), however, no accumulation of propionate was here detected. Indeed, there was no
424 evidence of inhibition in the CH₄ production evolution in preliminary BMP experiments carried out
425 with acidified FW rich in propionate (7.9 ± 1.4 g/L) (data not shown). The butyrate-rich acidogenic
426 effluent obtained from inoculated fermentations with pH control (32.7% VS loss) also underwent
427 faster methanization, suggesting that syntrophic butyrate oxidizers and acetate- and H₂-consuming
428 methanogens were extremely active, thus helping to maintain the H₂ partial pressure low.
429 Contrarily, the methanization of the acidogenic effluent originated from the self-fermentation with
430 controlled pH resulted in the lowest CH₄ production rate, which is a sign of inefficiency in the
431 transformation of organic matter to CH₄ by acetogens and methanogens, likely due to an imbalance
432 in the trophic microbial groups involved. However, it is not clear which factor was the rate limiting
433 step in the methanization of such acidified FW sample.

434

435 *3.3 Bioenergy production yield and rate*

436 A rational comparison between the one-stage and two-stage AD of FW was performed considering
437 the H₂ and CH₄ production yields and rates observed and the corresponding VS losses recorded
438 during the hydrolytic-acidogenic stage. The highest energy production yield of 11.4 ± 0.04 MJ/ton
439 VS added was achieved by digesting the lactate-rich acidogenic effluent, which was up to ~35%
440 higher than those yielded by the other two-stage scenarios. However, the one-stage AD of FW
441 yielded 13.0 MJ/ton VS added, which was 12.3–43.3% higher than those attained in the two-phase
442 configuration. This means that neither the superior CH₄ yield achieved through the two-stage
443 approach in comparison with that supported by the conventional one-stage AD, nor the recovery of
444 extra energy as H₂ gas offset the VS loss occurred in the first stage, even when VS losses amounted
445 only 16% of the initial VS content of FW. Bioenergy production in the form of H₂ accounted for
446 2.8–4.0% of the total energy, which is in line with H₂ productions previously reported in literature

447 (De Gioannis et al., 2017). Based on the properties of the real FW herein employed, the one- and
448 two-stage AD configurations tested yielded up to 4.4 and 3.9 MJ per each ton of FW digested,
449 respectively.

450 However, the AD of FW through an adequate two-stage process brought about clear
451 kinetics advantages to the process, which resulted in maximum global bioenergy production rates
452 between 1061 and 2890 MJ/ton VS fed-day (Fig. 5), corresponding to the range of 359 to 978
453 MJ/ton FW fed-day. The highest energy production rate estimated was recorded in the two-stage
454 AD of the lactate-rich acidified FW, despite the share of H₂ in this case was zero. The two-stage AD
455 using the effluent derived from the hydrolytic-acidogenic stage performed with inoculum but
456 without pH control resulted in a similar high bioenergy production rate (2748 MJ/ton VS fed-day or
457 923 MJ/ton FW fed-day), for which the H₂ productivity only accounted for 8.9% of the total energy
458 production rate. Such high specific energy production rates were almost twofold higher than the one
459 achieved in the one-stage process (1473.2 MJ/ton VS fed-day or 498.5 MJ/ton FW fed-day) (Fig.
460 5). The two-stage AD of the other two acidogenic broths resulted in slightly higher (9.2%) or even
461 lower (28.0%) energy production rates compared to that of the conventional one-stage AD plant,
462 notwithstanding the H₂ share amounted to 31.4 and 62.7%, respectively, of the total energy
463 production rate.

464

465 *3.4 Significance of the experimental data and future research*

466 Nowadays, the engineering of two-stage AD processes for the treatment of organic waste such as
467 FW with concomitant recovery of renewable bioenergy is gaining attention. The present study
468 confirmed that the performance of the first hydrolytic-acidogenic stage could influence both the
469 CH₄ production rate and yield. This study also showed that CH₄ production should be prioritized
470 over H₂ production in a two-stage AD process to maximize the overall bioenergy production. In this
471 regard, this study revealed the potential to attain superior bioenergy production rates compared to

472 the traditional one-stage scheme by modulating the acidogenic fermentation pathways towards a
473 primary lactate-type fermentation. In practical aspects, higher CH₄ production turnovers imply
474 lower retention times or higher FW treatment capacities in kinetics terms, which ultimately means
475 lower reactor volumes and reduced capital costs. In this context, long-term continuous operation of
476 lactate-based two-stage AD will be required to optimize the process and fully exploit the untapped
477 energy potential of FW. A large-demo scale study is also required to assess the economic and
478 technical viability of the lactate-based two-stage AD of FW proposed herein.

479

480 **4. Conclusions**

481 This study evidenced that a lactate-based two-stage AD process doubled the bioenergy recovery
482 rate from FW compared to one-stage AD. Additionally, this study showed that lactate metabolism
483 has a key role in the hydrolysis-acidogenesis of FW and demonstrated that both the biocatalyst and
484 culture pH are critical factors governing its fate which ultimately affects the methanization
485 outcome. Particularly, lactate as the major acidogenic end-product was only achievable in the self-
486 fermentation without pH control. Such tailored lactate-type fermentation solubilized particulate
487 organics while saving carbon and reducing equivalents. Contrarily, lactate consumption by
488 butyrogenic bacteria reduced the potentially available energy for syntrophic methanogenesis.

489

490 **Supplementary materials**

491 E-supplementary data of this work can be found in online version of the paper.

492

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498

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668 **Figure captions:**

669 **Fig. 1.** Effect of the operational pH and inoculum addition on the profile of cumulative biogas/H₂
670 production during the batchwise acidogenesis of FW. a) pH non-controlled with inoculum addition,
671 b) pH non-controlled without inoculum addition, c) controlled pH with inoculum, d) controlled pH
672 without inoculum. Each condition was assessed in duplicate, and the data points in the graph
673 correspond to the mean values and standard deviations (error bars). Solid lines represent the fitting
674 trend for H₂ production using the modified Gompertz model (Diaz-Cruces et al., 2020).

675 **Fig. 2.** Effect of the operational pH and inoculum addition on the profile of organic acids during the
676 batchwise acidogenesis of FW. a) pH non-controlled with inoculum addition, b) pH non-controlled
677 without inoculum addition, c) controlled pH (at 5.7 ± 0.1) with inoculum, d) controlled pH (at $5.7 \pm$
678 0.1) without inoculum. Each condition was assessed in duplicate, and the data points in the graph
679 correspond to the mean values and standard deviations (error bars).

680 **Fig. 3.** Observed microbial diversity (at genus level) in the inoculum (Ino), the substrate (FW) and
681 during the hydrolysis-acidogenesis of FW performed without pH control and with inoculum
682 addition ($W_{pH} + W_{Ino}$), without pH control and without inoculum addition ($W_{pH} + W_{Ino}$), with
683 pH control and with inoculum addition ($W_{pH} + W_{Ino}$), and with pH control and without inoculum
684 addition ($W_{pH} + W_{Ino}$). Local contribution to beta-diversity (LCBD) stands for a dissimilarity
685 coefficient; the higher the LCBD, the higher the dissimilarity among the analyzed samples.

686 **Fig. 4.** Time course of the accumulated methane produced (a) and daily methane production rate (b)
687 for the raw unfermented FW (control) and the four different acidified FW effluents. Solid lines in
688 figure (a) represent the fitting trends using the modified Gompertz model (Diaz-Cruces et al., 2020).

689 **Fig. 5.** Energy balance for the one-stage and two-stage AD scenarios. ERR: energy recovery rate
690

691 **Table 1.** Interplay effect between operational pH and biocatalyst on some process performance
 692 features recorded during the hydrolytic-acidogenic stage.

Condition	Uncontrolled pH & with inoculation	Uncontrolled pH & without inoculation	Controlled pH & with inoculation	Controlled pH & without inoculation
H ₂ yield (NmL/g VS fed)	31.2 ± 6.4	-	23.2 ± 9.9	16.3 ± 2.5
Peak H ₂ (% v/v)	53.4 ± 3.7	N.D.	46.1 ± 27.9	40.1 ± 9.0
Peak CO ₂ (% v/v)	46.6 ± 3.7	100 ± 0	53.7 ± 27.9	59.9 ± 9.0
CH ₄ (% v/v)	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
Total concentration of C released as CO ₂ gas (g/L)	2.7 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.2	3.3 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.3
^a <i>P</i> (NmL H ₂)	2062.8	-	1540.7	1075.0
^a <i>Rm</i> (NmL H ₂ /h)	52.9	-	71.8	233.4
^a λ (h)	1.7	-	21.3	25.8
R ²	0.9861	-	0.9990	0.9999
^b Total concentration of C measured as organic acids (g/L)	7.9 ± 0.5	9.7 ± 0.02	9.9 ± 0.3	10.5 ± 1.8
^b Organic acids concentration (g CODeq./L)	25.5 ± 1.7	26.6 ± 0.2	31.1 ± 0.04	32.9 ± 4.9
^b Organic acids yield (mg CODeq/g VS fed)	271.1 ± 17.9	283.5 ± 2.1	331.6 ± 0.5	350.4 ± 52.7
^c Acidification rate (%)	17.8 ± 1.2	18.6 ± 0.1	21.7 ± 0.03	22.9 ± 3.4
^d Electron equivalents disposed as H ₂ gas (e ⁻ meq)	261.8 ± 53.6	0	195.0 ± 83.0	137.1 ± 20.6
Final VS removal (%)	32.7 ± 7.2	15.9 ± 0.2	50.9 ± 3.6	42.6 ± 6.0

693 N.D.: Not detected.

694 ^a Kinetics parameters obtained from the modified Gompertz model; *P*: maximum cumulative H₂
 695 production, *Rm*: maximum H₂ production rate, λ : lag phase.

696 ^b Organic acids measured at the end of the hydrolytic-acidogenic stage.

697 ^c Acidification degree was estimated as the ratio (expressed in %) of the COD equivalent of organic
 698 acids measured at the end of the fermentation and the total COD of the substrate.

699 ^d 1 mmol H₂ produced is equivalent to 2 e⁻ meq.

700 **Table 2.** Modified Gompertz model parameters obtained for the different conditions tested.

Condition	pH control & inoculation	pH control & without inoculation	Without pH control & inoculation	Without pH control & without inoculation	Raw unfermented FW
<i>BMP</i> _∞ (NmL CH ₄ /g VS added)	430.6	438.6	408.7	376.9	397.2
<i>Rm</i> (NmL CH ₄ g/VS added-d)	43.3	26.5	109.9	97.6	42.0
<i>λ</i> (day)	0.8	2.9	0.5	0.2	3.2
<i>R</i> ²	0.9997	0.9937	0.9993	0.9983	0.9946

701 *BMP*_∞: ultimate methane production potential; *Rm*: maximum daily methane production rate; *λ*: lag

702 phase.

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Fig. 1

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Fig. 2

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Fig. 3

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Fig. 4

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Fig. 5